

Islamic Philosophy of Communication and Contemporary Globalization of Mass Communication: Similarities, Challenges, and Futuristic Scenario

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Abstract

Communication, sharing of the point of views with one another, is a very significant aspect of human's life. The ideology of Islam is also based upon communication. As the major guidance of Islam comes from Quran which is the fundamental mode communication of Allah with his Creators, Ahadith, followed by this, is an interactive mode of Hazrat Muhammad SAWW with his mankind. Islam has certain ways of communication that is hand-written, oral, through language, and through gestures as well. According to Islamic perspective, the most effective way of communicating with others is through a smiling face, shaking hands and hugging (among the same genders), wishing peace to one another by saying Salaam, keeping the balance between voice and tone, avoiding abusive language, using simple and understandable sentences, avoiding baseless arguments, and ending the whole conversations with paying greetings. Communication strategies are very much connected to the environment that we live in. During the ancient ages, ideas were communicated verbally and descriptively only. However, as the world advanced ways of communication progressed a lot and digitalization surfaced the entire globe. In the recent times, globalization of mass media has also progressed the ways of communication through social media platforms (Facebook, twitter, etc.), artificial intelligence, and cyber world. This globalization possess certain similarities with the tools of Islamic communication. Nevertheless, it has posed certain challenges for Islam as well. This study, therefore, intends to highlight the Islamic ideology, Globalization of communication, similarities between the two, along with the challenges of of later on the former. Research design being chosen in this study framework is futuristic analysis by reviewing the detailed concepts of Islamic communication and globalization of mass communication. That is why, this research study ends up with defining the futuristic scenario of Muslim world in the context of modern world's globalization.

Introduction

Prologue

Communication is a vital aspect of humanity that cannot exist without a stable communication medium. Islam is indeed a communication-based ideology, and yet, like any other religion, it faces several obstacles to develop and adapt to modernization and specifically to the social and economic influence of the ruling West. However, there is also an increasing interest for Islam as well as the number of followers has grown globally. The tendency to communicate efficiently is important for people to sort out their ideas and dreams. Furthermore, the Muslim community has been influenced by globalization and information technologies, even with its beneficial and harmful consequences. Islam is not opposed to globalization or even anti-globalization trend of human interaction. Communication as an empirical area of research has been regulated for several years by European beliefs that originated in the light of media interpretations in North America and Western Europe. Western communication concepts have been marketed around the globe as providing a heavy aspect of universalism. Recently, this methodology has been questioned on the grounds of misunderstanding the linguistic foibles of non-Western cultures as key elements of communication. The connection between interactions and cultural values is an extensively studied field of modern media literature. It has been suggested that, just as communication is a representation of cultural ideals and traditions, it is indeed an interpretation of civilization.

Absolute interpretation of the role of Holy Prophet (PBUH) has been distinctly stated by the Qur'an; it is a practical expression of the certainty of his Prophet Hood. The emergence of globalization has an effect on religion. While we live in an era where contact is becoming simple, it is also challenging. New technology has expanded the means of connectivity, and we are appreciating the benefits of such technological progress by maintaining contact with everyone. The rise of digital media technology is now a global trend. The human exposure to our own existence is something which digital communication technologies are not being able to replace by electronic means. It is interesting to note that the desire to connect is not confined among human beings; even our capacity to connect with our Maker, the Almighty Allah, has been indirectly affected by the speed of life which we are facing today. We feel ourselves in a rush to complete our prayers and take part in some very meaningless activities. We do not connect to our loving God in a way we should, as expressed in prayers of Prophet Muhammad (PBUH) as well as his fellows. Moreover, the most evident consequences of globalization and expansion of communication technologies are developments and innovations, both economically and culturally, that permeate the religious practices of the Muslims. Islam was never against globalization; Islam accepts the phenomena of globalization but also has a firm control of Islamic foundational rules. Yet, this globalization has caused many challenges to the recognition of Islam. This study entails the detailed description of Islamic concept about communication, the tools of Islam of communication including, written, verbal, language, etc. Moreover, extension in intercultural connections through communication has also been documented. Contemporary globalization of mass communication and challenges it has created for Islam have also been analyzed. In addition to this, the futuristic scenario for the Muslims states to confront and tackle this issue of globalization that is causing harm to the image of Islam is proposed.

Conundrum under analysis

The fundamental query being addressed in this research study is to investigate the Islamic philosophy regarding communication and contemporary globalization of mass communication. Similarities between the two domains are also set as the matter of interest and hence debated. Additionally, and most importantly, the challenges imposed by the contemporary globalization of mass media upon the Islamic image across the world has also been examined. In the context of whole discussion, proposing a way forward for the today's Muslim world to encounter and deal with the contemporary digitalized world should also be highlighted.

Study framework

Executing this research which is focused upon proposing a futuristic approach required the investigative analysis of several different primary and secondary sources that has been utilized in establishing the comprehensive understanding about the Islamic philosophy of communication. Quran, itself is a mode of communication between Allah and His creations through which He guided the whole humanity to lead their lives in an effective manner. This fact signifies the importance of communication in Islam at a greater extent. Moreover, in Islamic perspective, Sunnah and Ahadith (Acts and sayings of Hazrat Muhammad Mustafa SAWW) are also consulted as a preliminary resource for the above-mentioned purpose. Several academic articles penned by Intellectualists have also been studied and added herewith to advance the knowledge about Islamic way and effectiveness of communication. For understanding the contemporary globalization of mass communication for example social media, Facebook, twitter, artificial intelligence, and cyber world, different books are reviewed as a primary resource. Globalization, development, and the mass media by Colin Sperks is used to study about the role of mass media along with the other types of communication to bring about certain improvements in the contemporary globalized world. Another primary source been analyzed is the Myth of Media Globalization by Kai Hafez in which the most significant facets of mass communication across the globalized borders is discussed. Additionally, the tome titled, Introduction to digital media, described by Alessandro Delfanti and Adam Arvidsson has been reviewed to explore the contemporary digitalized world. Secondary sources inclusive of academic articles, newspapers, channel videos, and magazine articles are evaluated to explore the similarities between the communication tools of Islam and modern-day globalized societies. Moreover, most importantly, the challenges imposed by today's globalized arena on the image of Islam have also been researched and discussed. Finally, the research is concluded with putting forward a futuristic approach for the Muslim world to encounter and contemporary digitalization and in a sensible and peaceful manner, by keeping their religious obligation into consideration, to portray the real and true image of Islam at the global canvas.

Novelty of the study

To the best of my knowledge, this research study is the first in the nature of discussing the similarities and challenges among the communication tools utilized by Islam and the contemporary world with globalized mass communication. Moreover, in the light of those similarities and addressed challenges, futuristic scenario for Islamic portrayal has also been put forward.

Research queries

This research study is designed to inquire about the following questions:

1. What is the ideological approach of Islamic communication?
2. State the foundation and significance of education in Islam?
3. Give an overview of ancient Islamic communication.
4. How has globalized mass media hit the contemporary modernized world?
5. What is the role of mass communication in globalization in contemporary scenario?
6. How does the tools of Islamic communication cohere with that of modern-world's globalization?
7. How has present-day's digitalization challenged Islam?
8. Outlay the futuristic scenario for Muslim world in the context of contemporary globalization?

Concept of Communication in Islam

Interpersonal contact is characterized as a socialization characteristic in which individuals or groups communicate with each other on the basis of the development of shared goals. Inter-personal contact in Islam is basic and independent from any discrimination depending on ethnicity, color, language, faith, history, or nationalism. Islam is an ideology of interaction. The Islamic Lord is an interactional Lord Who has a strong interest in the activities of His people. Allah has addressed with mankind by the advancement of the prophets since Adam to His last Prophet—Muhammad (PBUH). The Islamic view on interpersonal contact, human activity and social interactions is that the independent human being could not secure anything required for his or her survival without the assistance of others. We may also claim Islam as a faith focused on contact. Allah has created humans with a basic role to interact. Allah states in the Qur'an:

○ عَمَّةُ النَّبِيَّانِ

"He has commanded him to speak (and to understand)" (Qur'an 55:4).

Prophet Muhammad (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) also used handwritten as well as vocal communication when needed. He used handwritten communications if data was to be preserved for later use or reference. However, vocal communication was used where knowledge had to be conveyed to individuals directly. Communication is important for transmitting messages as well as for the circulation of concepts. Indeed, interaction is essential for any progress to be capable of reaching out to audiences in attempt to fulfill our objectives. It is the innate nature of any person to interact, whether mute or deaf, by movement. Modern interaction is progressively seen as a medium by which the transmission and sharing of knowledge is facilitated. Similarly, various scholars described 'communication' through varied contexts. Some described it as promoting thorough understanding; however, others have claimed communication to be a means of understanding emotions. Some philosophers also represented it as a means of transmitting knowledge or messages from person to person. In Islamic culture, the term 'communication' is related to loyalty, purity of soul and spirit, respect, and reputation. Well-being for everyone and the counseling of belief in Allah are focused on the Muslim philosophy of communications. The duty of counseling and interaction was entrusted to the prophets in context of the Qur'an and Sunnah. However, since the completion of the prophet hood, this task is being entrusted to each person in Umma, so now it is the duty of the Muslim community to combat cruelty and spread righteousness by communicating effectively.

Foundation of Language in Islam

Islam has its faith in devotion and mode of living. Language is a means to comprehend these aspects. On this principle, each prophet was appointed for his community by conversing in their native language*. In the Holy Qur'an it was stated as follows:

وَمَا أَرْسَلْنَا مِنْ رَّسُولٍ إِلَّا بِلِسَانٍ قَوْمِهِ لِیُبَيِّنَ لَهُمْ فَيُضِلُّ اللَّهُ مَنْ یَشَاءُ وَیَهْدِیْ مَنْ یَشَاءُ ۗ وَهُوَ الْعَزِیزُ الْحَكِیْمُ

"We have not sent a messenger except in the language of his people to clarify 'the message' for them. Then Allah leaves whoever He wills to stray and guides whoever He wills. And He is the Almighty, All-Wise."[†]

Since Qur'an was presented in Arabic, the Qur'an is an evidence of His supremacy in the presence of various languages and races. However, Islam gives Arabic the status of a global language.

وَمِنْ آيَاتِهِ خَلْقُ السَّمَوَاتِ وَ الْأَرْضِ وَ الْخْتِلَافُ السِّنِّيَّتُمْ وَ الْوَاكِنُمْ ۗ إِنَّ فِي ذَلِكَ لَآيَاتٍ لِّلْعَالَمِیْنَ

"And one of His signs is the creation of the heavens and the earth, and the diversity of your languages and colours. Surely in this are signs for those of 'sound' knowledge." (Surat al-Rum, 22).

In addition, Imam Shafi'i stated, "Allah requires all human beings to understand Arabic, since communication between Allah and His creation is via Holy Qur'an and Allah has established the Qur'an recitation a mode of faith. Arabic is a standard language of Muslim community by rites and prayers. Qur'an and Sunnah are both the

* Ghofur, A. (2011, September 28). *THE ORIGINS OF HUMAN LANGUAGE Islamic Perspective and Science*.Kampungadris's Weblog.

† Quran Surah Ibrahim, verse 4

foundations of Islamic law, which is published in Arabic and includes details of the Arabic structure. Holy Prophet Muhammad (PBUH) stated:

“O mankind, truly God Almighty Keeper is one. Our ancestors’ also one (Adam), and true religion we are also one. The Arab of yours not on the basis of his father and mother, but the Arabian is because of the language spoken by the tongue. He who spoke Arabic, so he is an Arab.”

Qur’an is a genuine creation that cannot be reproduced, copied, and even predicted[‡]. It can be recited by people who read Qur’an in a language even though they cannot utter a single word in Arabic. Dr. Pasha, (2008) said that they have carried out some fascinating experimental studies on formatting and updating specific verses in the Qur’an but have stumbled, and the outcomes happened to be catastrophic. It is obvious it is as much evidence as humans are going to find in this universe of the fully spiritual essence of the Qur’an. This means that the main justification that no one is reluctant to complete the task of the Qur’an over time is that the Qur’an is a clear and perfect message of Allah Almighty in our fragile hands[§].

Overview of Ancient Islamic Communications

Oral communication

Prophet Mohammed (PBUH) transformed the people's religious, cultural and political institution. He belonged to the Quraish tribe. Muhammad (PBUH) was a rather introspective individual. He also escaped from a world he found manipulative and non-religious and devoted his time to sit alone inside a cave in Mount Hira. In this time of reflection, Muhammad (PBUH) found answers to religious issues that several intelligent Arabs had started to ponder. During such solo reflection, Muhammad (PBUH) sensed a command to reform the culture of the universe^{**}. Muhammad's first message from heavens arrived in the shape of an order:

اقْرَأْ بِاسْمِ رَبِّكَ الَّذِي خَلَقَ خَلَقَ الْإِنْسَانَ مِنْ عَلَقٍ اقْرَأْ وَرَبُّكَ الْأَكْرَمُ الَّذِي عَلَّمَ بِالْقَلَمِ عَلَّمَ الْإِنْسَانَ مَا لَمْ يَعْلَمْ

“Recite! In the name of your Lord, who created all things, who created man from a clot (of blood) and your Lord is Most Bounteous Who teaches by the Pen, teaches man that which he would not have otherwise known”^{††} (Qur’an 96:1-5)

The ancient Islamic community encountered a variety of cultural changes as it developed from a society of followers to a politically stable community then, finally, to a nation. Once Islam arrived in Arabia, vocal and face-to-face conversation with instant and continuous feedback was recognized as being the standard way of communicating. In an oral culture where few could read and write, creative forms of education and training were required. The face-to-face interaction between the Holy Prophet (PBUH) and his believers and companions established an important and special way of conveying Islamic values and actions through "observational learning". In the ancient Islamic culture, Muslims closely observed the actions and conduct of the Holy Prophet (PBUH) and followed him. The Prophet (PBUH) himself promoted this practice when he instructed his fellows and believers to "pray as he prays." This method was valuable due to the unfamiliarity of religion as well as its practices; however, most companions and believers were uneducated. The process of observational learning persisted well after the passing of the Holy Prophet (PBUH) as followers and associates continued to consult closely.

Allah also encourages us what we require to interact to make our voice the strongest. Allah states in the Qur’an:

وَمَنْ أَحْسَنُ قَوْلًا مِّمَّنْ دَعَا إِلَى اللَّهِ وَعَمِلَ صَالِحًا وَقَالَ إِنِّي مِنَ الْمُسْلِمِينَ

“And who is better in speech than one who invites to Allah and does righteousness and says, ‘Indeed, I am of the Muslims’.” (Qur’an 41:33).

In the following verse, Allah states that those who attract people to Allah are better at communicating. How wonderful is the Qur’an that teaches its followers to communicate so that it can be better. There are several cases of which oral speech has been adopted as an influential channel for public discourse, such as: Friday's Khutba and 'Khutaba-tul-wida', by far the most notable since the Holy Prophet (PBUH) explained significant religious and cultural problems in it, underlining fundamental concepts that have become significant for Islamic moral conduct. This is another clear example of the unique delivery style of the Prophet (PBUH) with its elaborate use of speech as well as the regular application of various rhetorical techniques, particularly analogy, idioms and similarity. One other illustration was the use of verbal communication for calling people to Salah (prayer) with many opinions and recommendations, however in the end it was Azaan that was implemented as a verbal communication method. However, when the population of Muslims grew, they addressed the issue about how to tell the timing for prayer by any popular means. Some proposed that fire be set and others recommended that an alarm be ringed. Bilal (R.A) had been instructed to enunciate the Azaan (Bukhari). Azaan

[‡]Brenner, L., & Last, M. (1985). The role of language in West African Islam. *Africa*, 432-446.

[§] Pasha, S. (1993). Towards a cultural theory of political ideology and mass media in the Muslim world. *Media, Culture & Society*, 15, 61 - 79.

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^{††} Qur’an 96:1-5

has been such a famous and influential method to remind people of Salah while they are involved in their temporal and private affairs. Presently, this communication is an eternal blessing of Islam

Written Communication

The role of composing and recording in social progress is highly stressed by a significant majority of language scholars. Composing has influence on both nature and humans, and documenting information promotes comparison and interpretation and facilitates the assessment and monitoring of natural events. In the Arabian Peninsula, people who can write and interpret are considered as socially superior and more dominant than people who are uneducated. As a communication-based faith, Islam has always highlighted and supported written communication. The perfect illustration of the application of written correspondence is the Qur'an, which was reported and maintained as it was published. It has been documented on stones, skeletons, palm leaves as well as animal skins. Following the passing of Muhammad (PBUH), the Qur'an was assembled into one volume by request from the Caliph Abu Bakr (R.A) and Umar (R.A). The very first recorded verse was a divine instruction to the Holy Prophet (PBUH) to read. Another significant evidence of the use of written communication is when the Prophet Muhammad (PBUH) introduced several rulers to Islam, however he could not reach anyone personally, so he adopted the method of written communication and posted letters by his companions. While Islam progressed and the Muslim community eventually became a state, interaction methods underwent a range of innovations that eventually contributed to the implementation of written correspondence and various tools to convey the ideology of Islam; they used brochures, journals, directories, etc., which contributed to the rise of the religion into a prosperous society

Ideological Approaches of Islamic Communications

Levels of communication and Social relationship in Islam

Communication can usually be studied at different levels that is personal, social, regional, medical, ecological, religious, financial, ideological and universal. Communication technology deals with the distribution of content to diverse populations by radio and television broadcasting, news agencies and a variety of other networks. Ideological communication is some communication strategy perceived to be political, as a result of its factual or possible implications for the workings of the ideological system. This is a personal interaction between the democratic establishment and the networking system. Social system is a mode of interaction and correlation in which knowledge is defined, communicated, changed and maintained. It is hard for an individual to resist interpersonal contact in society. Islam offers a characteristic way for people to communicate with each other. Interpersonal contact is a function of the society and culture in which individuals or groups communicate with everyone, in their behavior, people take into consideration how everybody is going to behave, and often citizens in the network work together in search of shared interests

Communication as a gateway to Intercultural Relations in Islam

A significant value of multicultural interaction is that Islam bestows on humanity the principle of dignity and fellowship. It was because of Muhammad (PBUH) that the universe received the groundbreaking message of basic humanity for the first time.

"O Mankind, your God is one and you have but one father".

There is almost no difference in Islam between personal and public behavior. A certain code of morality that one follows at home extends to one's actions in the society. This is valid for every organization of social system and every unit of state; everyone must comply with the principles of Islam. Islam does not acknowledge any distinction between the worldly and the divine, as man's compulsion to worship God and to fulfill His orders pervades every aspect of human life. Any move of man, his conduct and his morals is driven by his motivation that in the language of Islam is referred as *niyat* or aim. The aim or reason through which every act is carried out is the measure of its moral value. It seems appropriate to quote previous U.S. Attorney General Ramsey Clark (a person who has observed Islam thoroughly and has travelled widely around the Muslim world) and who, in 1955, addressed the following declaration to the Muslim as well as non-Muslim community: "Islam is the greatest opportunity the people around this world have with any hope of morality throughout their existence, for any promise of equality in their lives. It is the only progressive power that concerns for mankind." According to Qur'an, Muslims have the freedom to collaborate with all countries, regardless of their religion, and to condemn all types of racism, injustice, and violence. The Muslim world is empowered to collaborate with other communities to expand the objectives of harmony, prosperity, and human equality

Globalization in the contemporary Modernized world

Globalization applies to the growing integration of states and communities around the globe by investment, tourism, transport, culture as well as other modes of communication. Globalization in its technical sense is the method of evolving national or state events into international ones. It can be defined as a mechanism in which

people from all around the world are integrated in a common society and are able to work together. This system is a mixture of physical, technical, social, economic, and political groups. This transition has an impact on the environment, society, political processes, financial growth, stability, and well-being of the people in communities throughout the universe

Globalization of mass communication and Islamic communication

Nowadays, social networking has eliminated all the barriers and reasons that might be left to not communicate with someone we want to speak with. However, the pressures of everyday life have often made it extremely impossible to preserve regular interpersonal ties, which are an integral element of our spiritually recommended social existence. While we are all digitally connected to a broad circle of individuals, the more we learn about the dominance of e-mail services, the more we feel that something important is lost in our desire to interact so quickly. It is the natural "touch." It is the relationship and the desires that go with it with respect to physical contact and human capacity to interact with one's own self that is lacking. From eyes to ears, to various parts of body, we are capable of communicating, even without saying a word. Prior to modern period, the main centers of interaction in the Muslim community were their mosques, particularly during Jamaat or congregations, and markets, public spaces, and religious institutions. The mosque operated not only for daily prayers, however also for the transmission of facts and views as well as a platform for policy making. Recently, the international use of Internet has contributed to the fame of public networking sites. Facebook, Twitter, and YouTube are popular domains that have formed social systems where social communications are being proactively promoted. The growing involvement in this mode of information technologies has a profound influence on the cultural, financial, and ideological environment of international relations. However, the understanding of Islam as well as of Western views of the world has been questioned by this kind of online platform or modernization phenomenon. Modernization can be defined as acknowledging scientific knowledge, innovation, formal and rational ideas, and also being temporal, as seen in the most modern period of world heritage. Globalization often includes societal and historical ideals and has a profound effect on style. It has influenced Muslim youngster's minds, and processed food and designer brands is now trendy. A society that relies on feelings, but not souls, has been the core skill of globalization. Moreover, the idea of nuclear families, weakened living structures and relationships in Muslim cultures, as well as family planning, are also detrimental effects of globalization. However, religion in the life of a Muslim is the key binding factor in merging the world's largest ethnic groups and tribes, as it emphasizes the moral attitude, the righteous behavior and sacrifice for the sake of others, which evolved as the principles that contributed to the unity of different civilizations

Challenges and way forward

Western media is depicting an unreal and opposite image of Islam as well as the whole Muslim world. However, a practical strategy of response from the Muslim scholars and intellectualists is still not on the canvas through globalized media. This has generated and sustained damaging image of Muslims and Islam in the globalized World in the recent times. This dilemma is very concerning that if such image of Muslims and their religion continued to be built up without any accountability and investigation, like this, through the globalized media of western states, it may eventually lead to some sort of disputes among the global states. These disputes will resultantly lead towards terrible consequences for the civilization of whole humanity across the entire globe. To encounter the certain challenges imposed by contemporary globalization of mass communication, the leaders of Muslim Worlds are recommended to take certain actions.

- For example, they need to utilize the International peace forum of the world to dialogue about the true image of Islam.
- As the western globalized media is inculcating the negativity about Islam, which is encouraging the gestures of extremism, xenophobia, and Islamophobia at an international level.
- To tackle this the cyber department of Muslim worlds should take appropriate measures. The blasphemous content along with any feature that may lead to violent behavior among nations should strictly be banned.
- Islam is a religion of peace and spread peace all around, it has nothing to do with terrorism or terror-causing agencies like ISIS, Daesh etc. so the media tools portraying this picture of Islam should be judged, investigated, and sentenced accordingly.
- Also, at the national and international level globalized media should be utilized to portray the true image of Islam by establishing videos on Islamic history, delivering the lectures online by Islamic lectures, and sharing positive content by Muslim youth.

Conclusions

This research study is a theoretical systemization that has attempted to discuss in detail about the philosophy of Islam regarding communication. Communication possess a lead significance in Quran, as evidenced through various chapters and verses, as well as by the gestures and sayings of Hazrat Muhammad SAWW. Islam has proposed different modes to convey the ideas among one another. Allah has interacted with His creations

through the His book and 114 prophets since Adam to His last Prophet—Muhammad (PBUH). The opinion of Islam about interpersonal communication, human action, and social relations is that one human being alone is not able to get anything necessary for his or her existence without interacting with the other members of the community. The religion of Muslims- Islam endures devotion and guides effective ways of interaction and communication and language is one of them. Language is a mode of understanding the aspects of Islam in this regard. In accordance with the principle of language, Allah descended His prophets to teach their disciples through their native language. So that, they can understand the message of Allah. Communication also plays a significant role in intercultural relationships and these relations have widely been studied in contemporary literature related to globalized mass media. This significance proposes that communication equally represents cultural ideologies as well as traditions. Also, it is a mode of interpreting any civilization. For example, holy Quran, a mode of communication between Allah and mankind, is an absolute representation of Hazrat Muhammad Mustafa SAWW as a role model. However, the advancements in globalization has largely affect the image of religions- especially Islam around the globe. Though we are enjoying a time period with lots of advancements and technologies. Yet it is imparting challenge upon our global image as well. Advanced technologies has extended the modes of connectedness, in combination with it, we are appraising the uses granted by the revolution in technologies by expanding our relations with other people and nations. Islam is a religion of peace and believes in advancements of knowledge. That is why, it is true to state that Islam is not in contradiction to globalization. However, the threat posed by globalization to the real image of Islam is also not tolerable. Therefore, certain actions are required to taken by Muslim leaders, cyber worlds, and above of all Muslim scholars, to portray a real picture of Islam.

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